

REVIEW ON DISEASES WHICH ARE MENTIONED IN HOLY BIBLE

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Abstract:

DISEASES: di-zez', di-zez'-iz (chalah, choli; nosos): Palestine, from its position and physical conditions, ought to be a healthy country. The pious Jews recognized the hand of God in sending them, Psalm 39:9-11 90:3-12; and in many cases special diseases were sent in punishment of particular sins. The prevalent diseases in Bible lands were malignant fevers, cutaneous diseases, palsy, dysentery, and ophthalmia. Almost every form of bodily disease has a counterpart in the maladies of the soul. Several books and researchers defined no. of diseases in the bible, in this research we have to enumerate the number of diseases mentioned in holy bible in new version book concept. Research data collected from available research article from Google Scholar, Scopus, Science Direct and printed book of Holy Bible English new version. Collected data ordered to grouping the objective of this research then interpretation of the results and concluded this research by the relative citation score of each entity. Finally concluded as; Particular name: "disease" mentioned in 13 times in holy bible. 18 categories of diseases, and 12 diseases listed in 07. However, Altogether 88 diseases mentioned in the new version holy bible. Nowadays using name of diseases such as; Fever, Plagues, Leprosy, Tuberculosis, Menorrhagia, Blindness, Erectile Dysfunction, Osteoporosis, Carcinoma and Mental Disorders etc. were described in old testament and new testament in the holy bible.

Key Words: Diseases, Holy Bible, Kings & Sickness

Introduction:

Diseases: Were introduced into the world by sin, and have been greatly increased by the prevalence of corrupt, indolent, and luxurious habits. Besides the natural causes of diseases, evil spirits were charged with producing them among the Hebrews, Job 2:7 Mark 9:17 Luke 13:16 2 1 Corinthians 12:7. The pious Jews recognized the hand of God in sending them, Psalm 39:9-11 90:3-12; and in many cases special diseases were sent in punishment of particular sins, as Abimelech, Gehazi, Jehoram, Uzziah, Miriam, Herod, the Philistines, etc., and those who partook of the Lord's supper unworthily, 1 1 Corinthians 11:30. Christ manifested his divine goodness and power by healing every form of disease; and in these cases, as in that of king Asa, 2 Chronicles 16:12, it is shown that all the skill of physicians is in vain without God's blessing. The prevalent diseases in Bible lands were malignant fevers, cutaneous diseases, palsy, dysentery, and ophthalmia. Almost every form of bodily disease has a counterpart in the maladies of the soul.^{1-8,13-18}

DISEASE; DISEASES: di-zez', di-zez'-iz (chalah, choli; nosos): Palestine, from its position and physical conditions, ought to be a healthy country. That it is not so depends on the unsanitary conditions in which the people live and the absence of any attempts to check the introduction or development of zymotic diseases. The number of marshes or pools is fairly small, and the use of active measures to destroy the larvae of mosquitos might easily diminish or abolish the malarial fevers which now prevail all over the country.^{22-28,31} The freeing of Ismailieh and Port Said from these pests is an object-lesson in sanitation. When one examines the conditions of life in towns and villages all over the country, the evidences of the ravages of these fevers and their sequelae appear on every hand as they affect all ages from infancy to middle age, and one meets but few individuals of extreme old age. The absence of any adequate system of drainage and the pollution of the water supplies are also factors of great importance in preserving this unhealthiness.^{1,3,4,7}

In ancient times it was regarded as healthier than Egypt, as it well might be, hence, the diseases of Egypt are referred to as being worse than those of Palestine (Deuteronomy 7:15; Deuteronomy 28:60 Amos 4:10). The sanitary regulations and restrictions of the Priestly Code would doubtless have raised the standard of public health, but it is unlikely that these were ever observed over any large area. The types of disease which are referred to in the Bible are those that still prevail. Fevers of several kinds, dysentery, leprosy, intestinal worms, plague, nervous diseases such as paralysis and epilepsy, insanity, ophthalmia and skin diseases are among the commonest and will be described under their several names. Methods of treatment are described under MEDICINE; PHYSICIAN. The word "disease" or "diseases" in the King James Version is changed to "sickness" in the Revised Version (British and American) in 2 Kings 1:2; 2 Kings 8:8 Matthew 9:35, and left out in John 5:4; while in Matthew 8:17 "sicknesses" is replaced by "diseases." the Revised Version (British and American) also changes "infirmity" in Luke 7:21 to "diseases," and in Psalm 38:7 "a loathsome disease" is changed to "burning."^{17,19,5}

Diseases (38 Occurrences), 13 mentioned in 8 books and altogether 88 diseases like sickness mentioned in the holy bible. Therefore, several books and researchers defined no. of diseases in the bible, in this research we have to enumerate the number of diseases mentioned in holy bible in new version book concept.

Methodology:

Research type: this is systematic review

Research data collected from available research article from Google Scholar, Scopus, Science Direct and printed book of Holy Bible English new version.

Collected data ordered to grouping the objective of this research then interpretation of the results and concluded this research by the relative citation score of each entity.

Result:

Diseases in holy Bible:

- Disease, different forms
 - Leprosy, Fever, Boils, Palsy, Loss of appetite, Insanity, Epilepsy
- Mentioned in scripture
 - Plague, Emerods, Consumption, Dysentery, Lameness, Fever, Sun-stroke, Dumbness, Lunacy, Leprosy, Debility, Demoniactal possession, Palsy, Blindness, Loss of appetite, Deafness, Ulcers, Atrophy, Inflammation, Itch, Scab, Ague, Melancholy, Abscess, Issue of blood, Boils and blains, Worms, Impediment speech, Dropsy
- Other diseases mentioned
 - Chronic, Consumption, Emerods, Sun-stroke, Ulcers, Itch, Ague, Issue of blood, Dysentery, Dropsy
- Frequently
 - Tedious, Incurable, Painful, Loathsome, Complicated
- Those afflicted with
 - Often divinely cured, Anointed, Often laid in the streets to receive advice from passers, Often divinely supported
- Physicians undertook the cure
- Regarded as visitations
- Children subject
- Often sent as punishment
- Medicine used for curing
- Often through satan
- Art of curing, defective
- Not looking to God in, condemned
- Often brought from other countries
- Over-excitement a cause
- Illustrative of sin
- Sins of youth a cause
- Intemperance a cause

Disease, Different Forms of - Leprosy:

2 Chronicles 26:19 But Uzziah, with a censer in his hand for burning incense, was enraged; and while he was enraged with the priests, the leprosy broke out on his forehead before the priests in the house of the LORD, beside the altar of incense.

Leviticus 14:34 “When you enter the land of Canaan, which I give you for a possession, and I put a mark of leprosy on a house in the land of your possession,

Leviticus 13:2 “When a man has on the skin of his body a swelling or a scab or a bright spot, and it becomes an infection of leprosy on the skin of his body, then he shall be brought to Aaron the priest or to one of his sons the priests.

Leviticus 14:2 “This shall be the law of the leper in the day of his cleansing. Now he shall be brought to the priest,

Deuteronomy 24:8 “Be careful against an infection of leprosy, that you diligently observe and do according to all that the Levitical priests teach you; as I have commanded them, so you shall be careful to do.

Disease, Different Forms of - Fever:

Leviticus 26:16, in turn, will do this to you: I will appoint over you a sudden terror, consumption and fever that will waste away the eyes and cause the soul to pine away; also, you will sow your seed uselessly, for your enemies will eat it up.

Deuteronomy 28:22 The LORD will smite you with consumption and with fever and with inflammation and with fiery heat and with the sword and with blight and with mildew, and they will pursue you until you perish.

Acts 28:8 And it happened that the father of Publius was lying in bed afflicted with recurrent fever and dysentery; and Paul went in to see him and after he had prayed, he laid his hands on him and healed him.

Job 30:30 "My skin turns black on me, And my bones burn with fever.

Mark 1:30 Now Simon's mother-in-law was lying sick with a fever; and immediately they *spoke to Jesus about her. More verses: John 4:52

Disease, Different Forms of - Boils:

Job 2:7 Then Satan went out from the presence of the LORD and smote Job with sore boils from the sole of his foot to the crown of his head.

2 Kings 20:7 Then Isaiah said, "Take a cake of figs." And they took and laid it on the boil, and he recovered.

Isaiah 38:21 Now Isaiah had said, "Let them take a cake of figs and apply it to the boil, that he may recover."

Exodus 9:9 It will become fine dust over all the land of Egypt, and will become boils breaking out with sores on man and beast through all the land of Egypt."

Leviticus 13:18 "When the body has a boil on its skin and it is healed,

Mentioned in Scripture - Plague:

2 Samuel 24:21 Then Araunah said, "Why has my lord the king come to his servant?" And David said, "To buy the threshing floor from you, in order to build an altar to the LORD, that the plague may be held back from the people."

2 Samuel 24:25 David built there an altar to the LORD and offered burnt offerings and peace offerings. Thus the LORD was moved by prayer for the land, and the plague was held back from Israel.

2 Samuel 24:15 So the LORD sent a pestilence upon Israel from the morning until the appointed time, and seventy thousand men of the people from Dan to Beersheba died.

Numbers 11:33 While the meat was still between their teeth, before it was chewed, the anger of the LORD was kindled against the people, and the LORD struck the people with a very severe plague.

Disease, Different Forms of - Palsy:

Matthew 9:2 And they brought to Him a paralytic lying on a bed. Seeing their faith, Jesus said to the paralytic, "Take courage, son; your sins are forgiven."

Matthew 4:24 The news about Him spread throughout all Syria; and they brought to Him all who were ill, those suffering with various diseases and pains, demoniacs, epileptics, paralytics; and He healed them.

Matthew 8:6 and saying, "Lord, my servant is lying paralyzed at home, fearfully tormented."

Acts 8:7 For in the case of many who had unclean spirits, they were coming out of them shouting with a loud voice; and many who had been paralyzed and lame were healed.

Acts 9:33 There he found a man named Aeneas, who had been bedridden eight years, for he was paralyzed.

Disease, Different Forms of - Loss of Appetite:

1 Samuel 1:7 It happened year after year, as often as she went up to the house of the LORD, she would provoke her; so she wept and would not eat.

1 Samuel 28:23 But he refused and said, "I will not eat." However, his servants together with the woman urged him, and he listened to them. So he arose from the ground and sat on the bed.

Psalms 102:4 My heart has been smitten like grass and has withered away, Indeed, I forget to eat my bread.

Psalms 107:18 Their soul abhorred all kinds of food, And they drew near to the gates of death.

As like continue the results data in appendixes

Diseases of Kings in Bible⁴⁹:

No	Name of the King	Diseases	Modern Disease
1.	KING SAUL	mental disorder: manic episode with psychotic phases, major depression with psychotic features, mixed episode, bipolar disorder I, dysthymic disorder later developed into bipolar disorder, or non-specific psychotic disorder are the most likely	Bipolar Disorder, or Non-Specific Psychotic Disorder
2.	KING DAVID	Poor vision or blindness for thousands of years. The blindness, either age-related neovascular macular degeneration, or mature cataract, or asymptomatic open-angle glaucoma, or optic atrophy caused by the end-stage open angle glaucoma were the most likely responsible for the condition.	Open-Angle Glaucoma, or Optic Atrophy
3.		King David suffered from osteoporosis which affected his bones. Among the various diseases which may be associated with osteoporosis, the most likely are senile osteoporosis, hyperparathyroidism, or malignant disease.	Osteoporosis
4.		Among the numerous causes associated with weight loss, malignancy, social problems such as loneliness, social isolation and neglect by others, and psychological causes including depressed mood, were most likely responsible. With regard to malignancy, it seems that the King was affected by primary carcinoma of the prostate or kidney with subsequent metastases to bones.	Primary Carcinoma of the Prostate or Kidney

5.		Among the numerous causes associated with generalized weakness, cancer related fatigue, intractable bone pain, malnutrition leading to cachexia, severe anemia of chronic diseases, psychosocial problems associated with loneliness, social isolation, and neglect by others, and depression are the most likely. Among various diseases, the most likely to cause immobility and subsequent hypothermia are dementia, senile osteoporosis, hyperparathyroidism, or malignancy.	Generalized Weakness, Cancer Related Fatigue
6.		King David was afflicted by sexual dysfunction (SD). Among various types of SD, erectile dysfunctions (ED) combined with low or absent libido were most likely responsible.	Sexual Dysfunction, Erectile Dysfunction
7.		Major Depression, dysthymia, and minor depression seems the most likely	Major Depression, Dysthymia, and Minor Depression
8.	KING ASA	Peripheral vascular disease, gout, and degenerative osteoarthritis were most likely to affect the King's legs. Among these diseases, the diagnosis of peripheral vascular disease is the most acceptable.	Degenerative Osteoarthritis
9.	KING JEHORAM	Associated with prolapse of the bowel, colorectal carcinoma is the most acceptable. It seems that the colorectal carcinoma was poorly differentiated, invaded perirectal adipose tissue, blood vessels, and/or lymphatic vessels, and/or perineural areas, was lymph node positive and reached the fourth stage with the spread of metastases to the distal organs.	Colorectal Carcinoma
10.	KING HEZEKIAH	Anthrax is an often fatal bacterial infection, occurring in cutaneous, inhalational, gastrointestinal and meningeal forms.	Cutaneous Anthrax
11.	KING UZZIAH	The most likely are leprosy, leishmaniasis, neurodermatitis, or psoriasis. The intractable course of the disease, which necessitated placing the King in a separate house, where he remained until his death, points towards a severe, infectious disease.	Leprosy or leishmaniasis.
12.	KING ELAH	Chronic Alcoholism	Alcoholic intoxication

Discussion:

According to the results of this research, there was two major division of data collected as first one described the 18 categories of diseases, and second is 12 diseases listed in 07 kings in the holy bible. Altogether 88 diseases mentioned in the new version holy bible. Particular name: "disease" mentioned in 13 times in holy bible. Diseases entered as sick, Illnesses, punishments and inconsistency, etc. Hence, Fever, Plagues, Leprosy, Tuberculosis, Menorrhagia, Blindness, Erectile Dysfunction, Osteoporosis, Carcinoma and Mental Disorders etc. were described in old testament and new testament in the holy bible.

Conclusion:

Finally concluded as; Particular name: "disease" mentioned in 13 times in holy bible. 18 categories of diseases, and 12 diseases listed in 07. However, Altogether 88 diseases mentioned in the new version holy bible. Nowadays using name of diseases such as; Fever, Plagues, Leprosy, Tuberculosis, Menorrhagia, Blindness, Erectile Dysfunction, Osteoporosis, Carcinoma and Mental Disorders etc. were described in old testament and new testament in the holy bible.

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Conflict of Interest:

No any conflict of interest on this research.

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